

School Resources Management as Correlates of Teachers' Job Performance in Unity Schools in South-East, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated school resources management as correlates of teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria. Three search questions guided the study and three null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised 1,572 teachers in unity schools South-East, Nigeria. The sample for this study consisted of 472 teachers drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Two sets of instruments titled "School Resource Management Questionnaire, (SRMQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire, (JJPQ)" were used for data collection. The instruments were subjected to face and construct validation by three experts made up of two specialists in Educational Management and a specialist in Measurement and Evaluation all from Department of Educational Foundations in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. Cronbach Alpha which was used for test of the internal consistency of the instruments yielded overall coefficient of 0.86 and 0.91 for SRMQ and TJPQ respectively. The researcher together with six research assistants administered copies of the questionnaires to the respondents through a direct approach. A total of 472 copies of the questionnaire were distributed and 458 were properly filled and successfully retrieved indicating 97% return rate. Data collected was analyzed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research questions, simple regression to test the hypotheses. The finding of the study revealed among others that there is very high relationship between human resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. It was also found that... Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that school principals should human resource management units that overseeing, controlling and ensuring fair treatment of members of staff to motivate and improve the teachers' job performance.

Keywords: Resources Management, Teachers, Job Performance, Human, Material, Financial

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Introduction

Principals' effective and efficient application of the quality management principles will complement in their management of school resources. School resources according to Uzoechina (nd), refer to all human, material, non-material audio-visual environment and community materials available in the school to facilitate school administration and simplify the teaching-learning process. They also include other fundamental materials used in the school to make teaching very easy and learning more meaningful and comprehensible to the learners (Wada, 2014). School resources cover all those materials, human and non-human, drawn or photographed. Both manually or electronically operated books and all forms of related materials used in teaching and learning process (Waititu, 2017). School resources include the teachers in the school, human beings in the community, real objects, specimen or models, chalk and display boards, school buildings and layout, the community at large and other fundamental materials like pencils, pens, exercise books etc which the learners are expected to have at any point in time to facilitate learning (United States Agency for International Development [USAID], 2011).

Among the purpose of management in any educational organization is that of coordinating the efforts of people and the materials available towards the achievement of the goals of that organization. School resource management is the efficient and effective development of the school's resources when they are needed. Uzoechina (2016) described school resources management as the careful coordination of the resources available in the school system for the achievement of the schools goals. Such resources according to the scholar may include agricultural resources, inventory, human skills, production resources, or information technology (IT). Consequently, school resources management focuses on the administrative processes which include: budgeting, planning, staffing and reporting in order to achieve educational goals. In school environment, it is the duty of the head of department and leadership to maintain and effectively manage the school resources, and report back to the education board or any other controlling body. Educational resources are no doubt important in the development of a conducive teaching and learning environment. The use of these resources could give more valuable and powerful direction to the teacher than any personal effort without the materials. In school administration, school resources are not only limited but can be effectively and efficiently managed when management activities are properly harmonized, organized, coordinated and controlled by the school management team. This corroborates with Ayeni (as cited in Pobish et al., 2011) opinion that: it is

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not the availability of these resources above that guarantees effective performance of teachers and school in general, but their adequacy and effective utilization and management. However, no matter how well the school is provided with resources, without efficient and effective management of the available resources, the system may fail to achieve its desired result.

Secondary Education is the gateway to tertiary education and essentially provides greater number of lower level manpower needed for proper economic growth and national development (Adinna & Okafor, 2023). The quality of secondary education is a crucial issue that affects the development of individuals, communities, and nations (Okafor & Enemu, 2024). In the secondary school system, there are various resources needed for improving the teaching and learning activities to attain high quality of education. These resources are essential for improving teachers' job performance and overall school performance. According to Agenyi (2012), school resources are classified into four based on their nature. They include: human resources material/physical resources, financial resources, and time resources. This study adopted three out of the four identified variables by NOUN, and examined the relationship between them and teachers' job performance. The variables adopted included: human resources, material resources, and financial resources.

Human resources constitute a vital vein of any institution. The human resources in the school system include: teachers, support staff in the school, students, parents, community members and a host of other interest and social group. Uzoechina (2016) defined Human resources management as the planning, organizing, coordinating, controlling, manipulating and maintaining all personnel and stakeholders in education. Human resources are responsible for the management of other resources in the school. Human resources in the school are managed through recruitment, promotion, descriptive staff development, environment, evaluation, welfare services, transfer of staff, orientation and so on. Ahasanul et al. (2013) viewed human resources management as that part of management process that specializes in the management of people in work organizations. They maintained that human resource management emphasizes that employees are critical to achieving sustainable competitive advantage, that human resources practices need to be integrated with the corporate strategy, and that human resources specialists help organizational controllers to meet both efficiency and equity objectives. According to Arop et al. (2019), all activities of any institution are initiated by the persons that make up that institution. Plant, offices, computer, automated equipment and all inputs that the school uses are unproductive except for the human effort and direction. Human resources could be efficient, effective, and adequately utilized and managed if material resources are adequately provided.

Material resources are tangible resources that can easily be seen and observed in any institution. The material resources include: the structures, the machines, raw-materials, vehicles, and other tools; which can facilitate organizations' activities and processes. School materials would include classrooms, staff offices, vehicles, health centres, library, laboratory, and so on; which directly or indirectly contribute to the achievement of schools' goals. Material resources management has a direct impact on the learning environment and is a key determinant of educational outcome and teachers' job performance. Material resources management is the practice of coordinating the physical workplace and facilities by integrating the principles of business administration and architecture with the behavioural and engineering sciences. It is the application of scientific methods in the planning, organizing, coordinating, controlling, decision – making, supervision, and evaluation of the physical facilities in the school for the actualization of the school goals and objectives (Uko, 2015). These facilities are integral parts of the teaching and learning environment. Anyadike (2014) opined that material resources management is the scientific technique concerned with planning, organizing and control of flow and use of facilities from their initial purchase for the achievement of predetermined educational goals and objectives. It is therefore critical that school material resources management practices align with the school improvement plan by linking school assets to education service delivery standards and strategies. Just like material resource management, financial resources management is another category of school resources management identified in this study which is essential for improving teachers' job performance.

School finance is an aspect of school management. It is concerned with revenue allocation, disbursement of funds through budget allocation and alternative income into the school. School finance according to Aba et al. (2015) is a broad involving field encompassing three resource-related functions: revenue generation, resources allocation and resource utilization; all aimed at providing educational opportunities and producing educational outcome. School financial resources management covers such areas as the procurement of funds, their allocation, monitoring their use in the interest of accountability and producing report for the relevant stakeholders. Financial resource management is critical to effective management of secondary schools in Nigeria (Asogwa et al., 2018). Mifflin (2016) described financial resource management as the sum of money that has been set aside for a specific purpose. Financial resources can take any of the following forms: physical cash, credit facilities such as trade credits or bank credits, allowances or discount received, and various expenses such as differential expenses like taxes, rent, bills, undistributed profit in the form of retained earnings, receive, and so on (Asogwa et al., 2018). Financial management ensures prudence in the use of school funds to procure facilities necessary for effective job performance of members of staff.

Hitherto, it is apparent that reports corroborate the use of quality management principles for improving teachers' job performance. This suggests that application of quality management principles by principals is an important variable that can influence teachers' job performance positively. On the contrary, principals' poor management of school resources may be tantamount to improving teachers' job performance. In fact, scholars admitted that the non-implementation of quality management principles and poor school resources management by schools indicate a big obstacle to improving teachers' job performance and quality improvement of educational system; such that schools stand the risk of gradually becoming outdated. It is against this foregoing background that the researcher conceived the idea to investigate quality management principles and school resource management as correlates of teachers' job performance in federal government secondary schools in South-East, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Secondary school education in Nigeria is designed not only to provide sound and responsible secondary school graduates for low level employment but also to deposit in students' quality education potentials to succeed upon graduation. Regrettably, observation has shown that most secondary school students in Nigeria turn-out as half-baked graduates; who lack fundamental competencies for work. Many times, they do not meet the satisfaction of employers of labour, the stakeholders and the community at large. This problem is believed to have contributed to the high rate of unemployment and underemployment among secondary school graduates since a reasonable percentage of them comes out as unqualified graduates. This is an indication that secondary schools appear not to be attaining the goals and objectives for which they are established. It is also an indicator of possibility that the existing management practices by principals is inadequate. In addition, there is a growing anxiety that a relatively large number of public secondary schools across Nigeria are in poor conditions with worn-out machines, broken floors, overgrown with grasses, non-motivated teachers, inadequate and poorly managed facilities, poorly managed financial resources, examination malpractices and other disciplinary problems among the personnel. The poor state of the schools is adjudged to be determinate to the quality of education the students receive, and also responsible for poor students' academic achievement in both internal and external examinations.

Field visit to some of the federal government secondary schools in South-East, Nigeria revealed that some teachers and non-teaching staff in the zone appear to show little or no commitment in terms of carrying out their assigned duties. Some of them are more concentrated in organizing private lessons for students from wealthy homes while others engage in other private

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businesses. There are also cases of indifferent attitude among the staff towards co-curricular activities and other programmes in the schools. There are cases of bullying, lateness to school, destruction of school facilities, immorality and indecent dressing habits among the staff and students alike. These might be as a result of poorly managed school resources: as human resources, materials resources and financial resources are poorly managed by the school administrators. It is against this backdrop, that the study sought to investigate school resources management as correlates of teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study was to investigate school resource management as correlates of teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria. In specific terms, the study was intended to:

1. determine the relationship between human resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.
2. examine the relationship between material resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.
3. ascertain the relationship between financial resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between human resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria?
2. What is the relationship between material resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria?
3. What is the relationship between financial resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of probability:

1. There is no significant relationship between human resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.
2. There is no significant relationship between material resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.
3. There is no significant relationship between financial resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria.

Methods

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Correlational research design was adopted for the study. According to Nworgu (2015), this type of study seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. Correlation design is appropriate for this study because the researcher seeks to collect data from the given population of teachers to investigate the relationship that exist between school resource management and their job performance in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised all the 1,572 teachers in unity schools in South-East, Nigeria. The sample size of the study was 472 teachers drawn using proportionate stratified random sampling technique. Teachers in each state of the study formed a stratum from where 30% were drawn.

Two structured questionnaires titled: School Resource Management Questionnaire, (SRMQ) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire, (TJPQ) were used for data collection. The instruments were structured by the researcher based on the information gotten from the review of related literature and the specific objective of the study. SRMQ contained 30 items arranged in three Clusters namely: I, II and III. Cluster I contained 10 items on human resource management, Cluster II which centred on material resource management had 10 items and Cluster III contained 10 items on financial resource management. On the other hand, TJPQ contained 20 items which all measure teachers' job performance. The three sets of instruments were structured on a four-point rating of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D) and Strongly Disagree (SD) weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Face and construct validation of the instrument were established. The face validation was determined by three experts (two in the area of Educational Management and one in the area of Measurement and Evaluating) all from the Department of Educational Foundations in the Faculty of Education, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University, Igbariam campus. Construct validity was also conducted by the use of factor analysis with split-sample estimation involving the Varimax Rotation with Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) criterion of 1 and total percentage variance in the instrument was 343.307%. To determine the reliability of the instrument, a trial test was carried out using a sample of 20 teachers in unity schools in South-South Zone. The responses of the teaching staff were used to measure the internal consistency of items through Cronbach Alpha Statistics. The co-efficient of .862, .916 and .795 were obtained for clusters I, II and II of SRMQ with the overall reliability of .858 and coefficient value obtained for TJPQ was 906 which indicates that the instruments are reliable.

The researcher used direct delivery method to administer copies of the questionnaires to the respondents in their respective schools. This was done by the researcher with the help of six research assistants; who were briefed and instructed on how to distribute and retrieve copies of the

questionnaires from the respondents. Out of the 472 copies distributed, 458 copies indicating 97% return rate were duly filled, retrieved and used for data analysis. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient was used to answer the research questions and simple regression to test the hypotheses. Pearson (r) simple and multiple regressions were considered ideal for the study, because the study ascertained the extent of relationship between two or more variables in the study. For decision on the research questions, the coefficient r and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the correlation coefficient by Nworgu (2015) as follows:

Coefficient	Relationship
.00- .19	Negligible correlation
.20- .39	Low Correlation
.40- .59	Moderate correlation
.60- .79	Substantial
.80- .1.00	Very high correlation

In taking decisions on the null hypotheses, if p-value is equal to or less (\leq) than significant value of .05, the null hypothesis was rejected, but if p-value is greater than ($>$), the significant value of .05, the null hypotheses was accepted. All analysis was done using Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between human resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria?

Table 1: Pearson (r) on Relationship between Human Resource Management and Teachers’ Job Performance

Variables	N	Human Resource Management	Teachers’ Job Performance	Remarks
Human Resource Management	458	1.00	.846	Very High
Teachers’ Job Performance	458	.846	1.00	

As shown in Table 1, a Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) of .846 was obtained. This shows that there is very high relationship between human resource management and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This indicated that the increase in human resource management will lead to very high improvement on teachers’ job performance.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship material resource management and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria?

Table 2: Pearson (r) on Relationship between Material Resource Management and Teachers’ Job Performance

Variables	N	Material Resource Management	Teachers’ Job Performance	Remarks
Material Resource Management	458	1.00	.859	Very High
Teachers’ Job Performance	458	.859	1.00	

As shown in Table 2, a Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) of .859 was obtained. This shows that there is very high relationship between material resource management and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This indicated that the increase in material resource management will lead to high improvement of teachers’ job performance.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between financial resource management and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria?

Table 3: Pearson (r) on Relationship between Financial Resource Management and Teachers’ Job Performance

Variables	N	Financial Resource Management	Teachers’ Job Performance	Remarks
Financial Resource Management	458	1.00	.758	Substantial
Teachers’ Job Performance	458	.758	1.00	

As shown in Table 3, a Pearson’s correlation coefficient (r) of .758 was obtained. This shows that there is substantial relationship between financial resource management and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This indicated that the increase in financial resource management will contribute to substantial improvement on teachers’ job performance

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between human resource management and teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Table 4: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Human Resource Management and Teachers’ Job Performance

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Human Resource Management	.846	.716	1146.986	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 4, the simple regression coefficient (R) is .846 while the R² is .716 showing that human resource management makes 71.6% contribution to the variance in in teachers’ job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. The $F(1/458) = 1146.986$ and the p -value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance,

the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between human resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between material resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Table 5: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Material Resource Management and Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Material Resource Management	.859	.739	1288.749	.004	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 5, the simple regression coefficient (R) is .859, while the R² is .739 showing that material resource management makes 73.9% contribution to the variance in in teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. The $F(1/458) = 1288.749$ and the p -value of .004 is less than .05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between material resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant relationship between financial resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Table 6: The Summary of Simple Regression Analysis of the Relationship between Material Resource Management and Teachers' Job Performance

Predictor	R	R ²	F	P-value	Remark
Financial Resource Management	.758	.575	617.523	.000	*S

*Significant

As shown in Table 6, the simple regression coefficient (R) is .758, while the R² is .575 showing that financial resource management makes 57.5% contribution to the variance in in teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. The $F(1/458) = 617.523$ and the p -value of .000 is less than .05. Therefore, since the p -value is less than the stipulated .05 level of significance,

the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant relationship between financial resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study indicated that there is very high relationship between human resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This finding is in line with that of Uko, Umosen and Caleb (2015) which indicated that there was very high relationship between human resource management practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The possible reason for agreement between the findings is probably due to the fact that they are all conducted in secondary schools in the same country. Human resource management helps to develop and maintain healthy relationship in the school which enhances their job performance. The welfare facilities, recognition and incentives which is facilitated by human resource management induce teachers to work harder for higher job performance. Human resource management is highly correlated with teachers' job performance due to the fact that motivates teachers to put their efforts and time toward discharging their duties.

It was found that there is significant relationship between human resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This finding agreed with the report of Onafadeji, Ogunyemi and AlarapeBabatunde (2017) which revealed that there was significant relationship between human resource management practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. This agreed with the finding of Kamaldeen, Oluyemisi, Busayo, Abdulrafiu and Laro (2020) who reported that there was a significant relationship between human resource management and teachers' job performance. The possible explanation for the agreement in findings is that the two studies were conducted in the same country.

The result of the study indicated that there is very high relationship between material resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This finding agreed with that of Uko, Umosen and Caleb (2015) which indicated that there was a very high relationship between material resource management practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The possible reason for agreement between the findings is probably due to the fact that they are all conducted in secondary schools in the same country. Material resource management is highly correlated with teachers' job performance due to the fact that the availability of adequate physical facilities creates favourable work environment. The provision of sufficient instructional materials and well-equipped offices induce them to effectively present their lessons

in the classroom. The maintenance and effective utilization of material resources in teaching the students contribute to the improvement on the job performance of teachers.

It was reported that there is significant relationship between material resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This agreed with the report of Uko, Umosen and Caleb (2015) which indicated that there was significant relationship between material resource management practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The possible reason for agreement between the findings is probably due to the fact that they are all conducted in secondary schools in the same country.

It was reported that there is substantial relationship between financial resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This finding disagreed with that of Uko, Umosen and Caleb (2015) which showed that there was very high relationship between financial resource management practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The possible reason for disagreement between the findings is probably due to the fact that there is variation in financial allocation and budget in secondary schools in different states in which the two studies were conducted. Financial resource management has substantial relationship with teachers' job performance due to the fact that judicious use of school funds builds healthy work environment. Financial allocation according to school needs, proper monitoring of expenditure and prudent accountability are financial management principles that have substantially relationship with teachers' job performance.

It was revealed that there is significant relationship between financial resource management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. This agreed with the report of Uko, Umosen and Caleb (2015) which indicated that there was significant relationship between financial resource management practices and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The possible reason for agreement between the findings is probably due to the fact that they are all conducted in secondary schools in the same country.

Conclusion

From the findings of the study, it is concluded that there is very high positive correlation between school resources management and teachers' job performance in unity schools in South-east, Nigeria. Resources managements are geared that ensuring that human, material and financial resources are put into effective use to improve the job performance of teachers.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made based on the results of the study:

1. Unity school principals should human resource management units that overseeing, controlling and ensuring fair treatment of members of staff to motivate and improve the teachers' job performance.
2. School principals should engage in regular inspection of materials resources for possible maintenance which keeps them in functional state for utilization by teachers to improve their job performance.
3. The school principals engage in annual budgeting, accounting and auditing exercise to ensure judicious use of school funds in providing facilities which improve the job performance of teachers.

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